

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF GINGEROL AS VESICULAR DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS (NIOSOMES) USING REVERSE-PHASE EVAPORATION TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to formulate and evaluate niosomal drug delivery systems containing 6-gingerol, a bioactive compound known for its anti-cancer properties. Using reverse-phase evaporation technique, eight formulations (F1-F8) were developed employing varying combinations of non-ionic surfactants (Span 80, Tween 20, and Tween 80) and cholesterol. The formulations were assessed for encapsulation efficiency, vesicle size, shape, and in-vitro drug release. Results indicated that formulations with higher molecular weight surfactants exhibited superior encapsulation efficiency and sustained drug release, highlighting their potential as effective delivery systems for 6-gingerol.

KEYWORDS: 6-gingerol, niosomes, reverse-phase evaporation, encapsulation efficiency, sustained release.

INTRODUCTION

Cancer is a leading cause of death worldwide, characterized by the uncontrolled growth of abnormal cells that can invade surrounding tissues and spread to other body parts. Conventional cancer treatments, such as chemotherapy, radiotherapy, and surgery, are often limited by severe side effects, drug resistance, and non-specificity. Therefore, there is an

urgent need for alternative therapeutic approaches with enhanced efficacy and reduced toxicity. 6-gingerol, the principal bioactive component of ginger (*Zingiber officinale*), has garnered attention for its diverse pharmacological properties, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and anti-cancer activities. Despite its therapeutic potential, 6-gingerol's clinical application is constrained by poor water solubility, low bioavailability, and rapid clearance.

Niosomes, non-ionic surfactant-based vesicular carriers, have emerged as a versatile drug delivery system for hydrophobic drugs like 6-gingerol. These biocompatible carriers enhance drug solubility, improve bioavailability, and allow controlled drug release, thus minimizing systemic toxicity. This study aims to formulate and evaluate 6-gingerol-loaded niosomes using different surfactant compositions to determine the optimal formulation for sustained release and maximum therapeutic efficacy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MATERIALS

6-gingerol (95% purity) from Venkatesh Food Industry, Madhya Pradesh. Cholesterol, Span 80, Tween 20, Tween 80, and diethyl ether from Sri Sai Chemicals, Vizag. Phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4) All chemicals used were of analytical grade.

PREPARATION OF NIOSOMES

The reverse-phase evaporation technique was employed to prepare the niosomal formulations. Cholesterol and surfactants were dissolved in a mixture of chloroform and diethyl ether. The aqueous phase containing 6-gingerol was added, and the resulting mixture was sonicated to form a stable emulsion. The organic solvents were removed using a rotary evaporator under reduced pressure to yield a viscous niosomal suspension. The suspension was hydrated with PBS (pH 7.4) and further homogenized at 60°C to form uniform vesicles.

FORMULATION COMPOSITION

Eight formulations (F1-F8) were designed with varying combinations of Span 80, Tween 20, and Tween 80 as surfactants, along with cholesterol. F1 served as a control without any surfactants.

Table 1: Different formulations of Gingerol niosomes.

S.No.	Ingredients	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	F ₄	F ₅	F ₆	F ₇	F ₈
1.	Gingerol	500mg							
2.	Cholesterol	500mg							

3.	Span 80	-	500mg	-	500mg	-	500mg	-	500mg
4.	Tween 20	-	-	500mg	500mg	-	-	500mg	500mg
5.	Tween 80	-	-	-	-	500mg	500mg	500mg	500mg
6.	Cetyl pyridinium chloride	65mg	65mg	65mg	65mg	65mg	65mg	65mg	65mg
7.	Diethyl ether	15ml	15ml	15ml	15ml	15ml	15ml	15ml	15ml

CHARACTERIZATION OF NIOSOMES

VESICLE SIZE AND MORPHOLOGY

Vesicle size was measured using optical microscopy and confirmed with scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Morphological analysis confirmed the spherical structure of the vesicles.

ENCAPSULATION EFFICIENCY (EE)

Encapsulation efficiency was calculated by centrifugation at 15,000 rpm for 45 minutes to separate encapsulated 6-gingerol. The encapsulated drug concentration was determined spectrophotometrically at 282 nm.

IN-VITRO DRUG RELEASE

Drug release studies were performed using dialysis membrane bags immersed in PBS at 37°C under continuous stirring. Samples were withdrawn at regular intervals and analyzed spectrophotometrically.

RESULTS

VESICLE SIZE AND MORPHOLOGY

Formulations F2-F8 exhibited vesicles with sizes ranging from $3.64 \pm 0.35 \mu\text{m}$ to $5.83 \pm 0.71 \mu\text{m}$. The largest vesicles were observed in F8, attributed to the combined use of Span 80, Tween 20, and Tween 80, which enhanced bilayer stability. SEM images confirmed the spherical and uniform morphology of the vesicles.

Figure 1: Microscopy of Gingerol Niosome.

ENCAPSULATION EFFICIENCY

Encapsulation efficiencies ranged from 35.69% (F3) to 69.6% (F8). Formulations containing a combination of surfactants displayed higher EE compared to single-surfactant formulations, with cholesterol further stabilizing the bilayer and enhancing entrapment.

Table 2: Encapsulation Efficiency & Vesicle Diameter of the formulations.

S. No.	Formulation	%EE	Vesicle Diameter (μm)
1.	F ₁	—	—
2.	F ₂ (Span 80)	43.20%	4.27 \pm 0.49
3.	F ₃ (Tween 20)	35.69%	3.64 \pm 0.35
4.	F ₄ (Span 80 & Tween 20)	38.23%	4.60 \pm 0.43
5.	F ₅ (Tween 80)	57.35%	4.42 \pm 0.51
6.	F ₆ (Span 80 & Tween 80)	65.78%	5.31 \pm 0.60
7.	F ₇ (Tween 20 & Tween 80)	60.6%	4.75 \pm 0.58
8.	F ₈ (Span 80, Tween 20 & Tween 80)	69.6%	5.83 \pm 0.71

%EE = % Encapsulation Efficiency

IN-VITRO DRUG RELEASE STUDIES

F8 demonstrated a sustained release of 6-gingerol over 24 hours, achieving 100.03% cumulative release. Formulations F2 and F5 exhibited controlled release for up to 20 hours. F3 released the drug within 14 hours due to the hydrophilic nature of Tween 20, leading to faster diffusion. Mixed surfactant formulations (e.g., F6 and F8) displayed prolonged release profiles, highlighting the synergistic effects of surfactants in maintaining bilayer integrity.

Table 3: Results of Formula F₂ (SPAN 80).

S. No.	Time (H)	Absorbance	Dilution factor	Cumulative amount dissolved (mg)	Cumulative % Drug Dissolved	Cumulative % Drug Undissolved	Cumulative Log % Undissolved
1	1	0.098	-	1.15	7.66	92.34	1.96
2	2	0.172	-	2.02	13.46	86.54	1.93
3	3	0.273	-	3.21	21.4	78.6	1.89
4	4	0.403	-	4.74	31.6	68.4	1.83
5	5	0.467	-	5.49	36.6	63.4	1.80
6	6	0.564	-	6.63	44.2	55.8	1.74
7	7	0.676	-	7.95	53	47	1.67
8	8	0.075	10	8.82	58.8	41.2	1.61
9	9	0.083	10	9.76	65.06	34.94	1.54
10	10	0.092	10	10.82	72.13	27.87	1.44
11	11	0.097	10	11.41	76.06	23.94	1.37
12	12	0.103	10	12.11	80.86	19.14	1.28
13	13	0.107	10	12.58	83.86	16.14	1.20
14	14	0.111	10	13.05	87	13	1.11
15	15	0.114	10	13.41	89.4	10.6	1.02

16	16	0.117	10	13.76	91.7	8.3	0.91
17	17	0.120	10	14.11	94	6	0.77
18	18	0.123	10	14.47	96.4	3.6	0.55
19	19	0.128	10	15.05	100.3	0	-

Figure 2: Dissolution profile of F2.

Table 4: Results of Formula F₃ (TWEEN 20).

S. No.	Time (H)	Absorbance	Dilution factor	Cumulative amount dissolved (mg)	Cumulative % Drug Dissolved	Cumulative % Drug Undissolved	Cumulative Log % Undissolved
1	1	0.115	-	1.35	9	91	1.95
2	2	0.198	-	2.32	15.4	84.6	1.92
3	3	0.309	-	3.63	24.2	75.8	1.87
4	4	0.457	-	5.37	35.8	64.2	1.80
5	5	0.521	-	6.12	40.8	59.2	1.77
6	6	0.630	-	7.42	49.5	50.5	1.70
7	7	0.076	10	8.94	59.6	40.4	1.60
8	8	0.090	10	10.58	70.5	29.5	1.46
9	9	0.100	10	11.76	78.4	21.6	1.33
10	10	0.106	10	12.47	83	17	1.23
11	11	0.117	10	13.76	91.17	8.3	0.91
12	12	0.122	10	14.35	95.6	4.4	0.64
13	13	0.127	10	14.7	98	2	0.30
14	14	0.129	10	15.1	100.3	0	-

Figure 3: Dissolution Profile of F3 (Tween 20).

Table 4: Results of Formula_{F4} (SPAN 80+ TWEEN 20).

S. No.	Time (H)	Absorbance	Dilution factor	Cumulative amount dissolved(mg)	Cumulative % Drug Dissolved	Cumulative % Drug Undissolved	Cumulative Log % Undissolved
1	1	0.096	-	1.12	7.46	92.54	1.96
2	2	0.181	-	2.12	14.3	85.87	1.93
3	3	0.264	-	3.10	20.6	79.4	1.89
4	4	0.401	-	4.71	31.4	68.6	1.83
5	5	0.463	-	5.44	36.2	63.8	1.80
6	6	0.531	-	6.24	41.6	58.4	1.76
7	7	0.648	-	7.62	50.8	49.2	1.69
8	8	0.071	10	8.35	55.6	44.4	1.64
9	9	0.084	10	9.8	65.3	34.7	1.54
10	10	0.091	10	10.7	71.3	28.7	1.45
11	11	0.101	10	11.8	78.6	21.4	1.33
12	12	0.106	10	12.4	82.6	17.4	1.24
13	13	0.109	10	12.82	85.5	14.5	1.16
14	14	0.112	10	13.17	87.8	12.2	1.08
15	15	0.115	-	13.52	90.1	9.9	0.99
16	16	0.118	-	13.88	92.5	7.5	0.87
17	17	0.120	-	14.11	94	6	0.77
18	18	0.123	-	14.47	96.4	3.6	0.55
19	19	0.126	-	14.82	98.8	1.2	0.07
20	20	0.128	-	15.05	100.3	0	-

Figure 4: Dissolution Profile of F4 (SPAN 80 + TWEEN 20).

Table 5: Results of Formula F₅ (TWEEN 80).

S. No.	Time (H)	Absorbance	Dilution factor	Cumulative amount dissolved (mg)	Cumulative % Drug Dissolved	Cumulative % Drug Undissolved	Cumulative Log % Undissolved
1	1	0.101	-	1.18	7.86	92.14	1.96
2	2	0.178	-	2.09	13.9	86.1	1.93
3	3	0.284	-	3.35	22.2	77.8	1.89
4	4	0.420	-	4.94	32.9	67.1	1.82
5	5	0.491	-	5.77	38.4	61.6	1.78
6	6	0.584	-	6.87	45.8	54.2	1.73
7	7	0.685	-	8.05	53.6	46.4	1.66

8	8	0.080	10	9.41	62.7	37.3	1.57
9	9	0.091	10	10.70	71.3	28.7	1.45
10	10	0.098	10	11.52	76.8	23.2	1.36
11	11	0.102	10	12	80	20	1.30
12	12	0.108	10	12.70	84.6	15.4	1.18
13	13	0.112	10	13.17	87.8	12.2	1.08
14	14	0.114	10	13.41	89.4	10.6	1.02
15	15	0.117	10	13.76	91.7	8.3	0.91
16	16	0.121	10	14.23	94.2	5.8	0.76
17	17	0.124	10	14.58	97.2	2.8	0.44
18	18	0.127	10	14.94	99.6	0.4	-

Figure 5: Dissolution Profile of F5 (Tween 80).

Table 6: Results of Formula F₆ (SPAN 80 + TWEEN 80).

S. No.	Time (H)	Absorbance	Dilution factor	Cumulative amount dissolved (mg)	Cumulative % Drug Dissolved	Cumulative % Drug Undissolved	Cumulative Log % Undissolved
1	1	0.089	-	1.04	6.93	93.07	1.96
2	2	0.149	-	1.75	11.6	88.4	1.94
3	3	0.221	-	2.6	17.3	82.7	1.91
4	4	0.331	-	3.89	26	74	1.86
5	5	0.413	-	4.85	32.3	67.7	1.83
6	6	0.481	-	5.65	37.6	62.4	1.79
7	7	0.563	-	6.62	44.1	55.9	1.74
8	8	0.620	-	7.29	48.6	51.4	1.71
9	9	0.691	-	8.12	54.13	45.87	1.66
10	10	0.079	10	9.29	61.9	38.1	1.58
11	11	0.088	10	10.35	69	31	1.49
12	12	0.093	10	10.94	72.9	27.1	1.43
13	13	0.101	10	11.88	79.2	20.8	1.31
14	14	0.103	10	12.11	80.7	19.3	1.28
15	15	0.107	10	12.58	83.8	16.2	1.20
16	16	0.109	10	12.82	85.4	14.6	1.16
17	17	0.112	10	13.17	87.8	12.2	1.08
18	18	0.116	10	13.64	90.9	9.1	0.95
19	19	0.119	10	14	93.3	6.7	0.82
20	20	0.122	10	14.35	95.6	4.4	0.64
21	21	0.126	10	14.8	98.6	1.4	0.14

S. No.	Time (H)	Absorbance	Dilution factor	Cumulative amount dissolved (mg)	Cumulative % Drug Dissolved	Cumulative % Drug Undissolved	Cumulative Log % Undissolved
22	22	0.128	10	15.05	100.3	0	-
23	23	-	-	-	-	-	-
24	24	-	-	-	-	-	-

Figure 6: Dissolution Profile of F6 (Span 80 + Tween 80).

Table 7: Results of Formula F7 (TWEEN 20 + TWEEN 80).

S. No.	Time (H)	Absorbance	Dilution factor	Cumulative amount dissolved (mg)	Cumulative % Drug Dissolved	Cumulative % Drug Undissolved	Cumulative Log % Undissolved
1	1	0.094	-	1.10	7.3	92.7	1.96
2	2	0.169	-	1.98	13.2	86.8	1.93
3	3	0.270	-	3.17	21.1	78.9	1.89
4	4	0.417	-	4.90	32.6	67.4	1.82
5	5	0.484	-	5.69	38	62	1.79
6	6	0.569	-	6.69	44.6	55.4	1.74
7	7	0.665	-	7.82	52.1	47.9	1.68
8	8	0.076	10	8.94	59.6	40.4	1.60
9	9	0.089	10	10.47	69.8	30.2	1.48
10	10	0.096	10	11.29	75.2	24.8	1.39
11	11	0.102	10	12	80	20	1.30
12	12	0.107	10	12.58	83.8	16.2	1.20
13	13	0.110	10	12.94	86.26	13.74	1.13
14	14	0.113	10	13.2	88.6	11.4	1.05
15	15	0.117	10	13.7	91.7	8.3	0.91
16	16	0.119	10	14	93.3	6.7	0.82
17	17	0.121	10	14.2	94.8	5.2	0.71
18	18	0.123	10	14.4	96.4	3.6	0.55
19	19	0.125	10	14.7	98	2	0.30
20	20	0.127	-	14.9	99.6	0.4	-
21	21	-	-	-	-	-	-

22	22	-	-	-	-	-	-
23	23	-	-	-	-	-	-
24	24	-	-	-	-	-	-

Figure 7: Dissolution Profile of F7 (Tween 20 + Tween 80).

Table 8: Results of Formula F₈ (SPAN 80 + TWEEN 20 + TWEEN 80).

S. No.	Time (H)	Absorbance	Dilution factor	Cumulative amount dissolved (mg)	Cumulative % Drug Dissolved	Cumulative % Drug Undissolved	Cumulative Log % Undissolved
1	1	0.081	-	0.95	6.33	93.7	1.97
2	2	0.146	-	1.71	11.4	88.6	1.94
3	3	0.214	-	2.51	16.7	83.3	1.92
4	4	0.321	-	3.77	25.13	74.87	1.87
5	5	0.404	-	4.75	31.6	68.4	1.83
6	6	0.473	-	5.56	37	63	1.79
7	7	0.550	-	6.47	43.12	56.87	1.75
8	8	0.611	-	7.18	47.8	52.2	1.71
9	9	0.682	-	8.02	53.4	46.6	1.66
10	10	0.075	10	8.82	58.8	41.2	1.61
11	11	0.084	10	9.88	65.8	34.2	1.53
12	12	0.089	10	10.47	69.8	30.2	1.48
13	13	0.093	10	10.94	72.9	27.1	1.43
14	14	0.096	10	11.29	75.2	24.8	1.39
15	15	0.099	10	11.64	77.6	22.4	1.35
16	16	0.102	10	12	80	20	1.30
17	17	0.109	10	12.82	84.6	15.4	1.18
18	18	0.111	10	13.05	87	13	1.11
19	19	0.114	10	13.41	89.4	10.6	1.02
20	20	0.117	10	13.76	91.7	8.3	0.91
21	21	0.119	10	14	93.3	6.7	0.82
22	22	0.121	10	14.23	94.8	5.2	0.71
23	23	0.124	10	14.58	97.2	2.8	0.44
24	24	0.128	10	15.05	100.03	0	-

Figure 8: Dissolution Profile of F8 (Span 80+Tween 20+Tween 80).

Table 9: OTHER DISSOLUTION PARAMETERS.

S.No.	Formulation	K_0	K_1	R
1.	F ₁ (No surfactant)	-	-	-
2.	F ₂ (Span 80)	0.8011	0.1382	0.962
3.	F ₃ (Tween 20)	1.150	0.1952	0.981
4.	F ₄ (Span 80+ Tween 20)	0.777	0.1643	0.948
5.	F ₅ (Tween 80)	0.857	0.1934	0.958
6.	F ₆ (Span 80+ Tween 80)	0.7008	0.1982	0.969
7.	F ₇ (Tween 20 +Tween 80)	0.7699	0.2703	0.943
8.	F ₈ (Span 80+Tween 20+ Tween 80)	0.6250	0.1738	0.959

{Rate constant (Zero Order) [K_0]};

{Rate constant (First Order) [K_1]};

{Regression [R]}:

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In this study, three distinct non-ionic surfactants were combined with cholesterol to develop gingerol niosomes. Gingerol is known for its ability to inhibit tumor growth in cancer. The niosomes were prepared using the reverse phase evaporation technique and subsequently suspended in phosphate buffer at pH 7.4 for further evaluation. The final formulation appeared as a yellow-colored suspension. Formulation F1 did not yield niosomes due to the absence of a surfactant, which is essential for vesicle formation. However, niosomal structures were observed under a microscope for the other formulations. Vesicle diameters

for formulations F2 to F8 were measured using optical microscopy with an eyepiece and stage micrometer, yielding the following results: F2 ($4.27 \pm 0.49 \mu\text{m}$), F3 ($3.64 \pm 0.35 \mu\text{m}$), F4 ($4.60 \pm 0.43 \mu\text{m}$), F5 ($4.42 \pm 0.51 \mu\text{m}$), F6 ($5.31 \pm 0.60 \mu\text{m}$), F7 ($4.75 \pm 0.53 \mu\text{m}$), and F8 ($5.83 \pm 0.71 \mu\text{m}$). Among these, formulation F8 exhibited the largest vesicle diameter. The order of vesicle diameters was $F8 > F6 > F7 > F4 > F5 > F2 > F3$. The data indicated that surfactants with higher molecular weights produced larger vesicles, whereas those with lower molecular weights resulted in smaller vesicles.

Encapsulation efficiency was also evaluated, with the following results: F2 (43.20%), F3 (36.69%), F4 (38.23%), F5 (57.35%), F6 (65.78%), F7 (60.60%), and F8 (69.90%). Formulation F8 showed the highest drug entrapment. The order of encapsulation efficiency was $F8 > F6 > F7 > F4 > F5 > F2 > F3$. This pattern suggested that higher molecular weight surfactants achieved greater drug encapsulation compared to their lower molecular weight counterparts.

An *in vitro* dissolution study was performed using the dialysis membrane method. The dissolution profiles indicated that formulation F8, which contained three surfactants, exhibited the most controlled drug release over 24 hours. Formulations F4, F6, and F7, which incorporated two surfactants, showed controlled release for approximately 20 hours. In contrast, formulations F2 and F5, with single surfactants, exhibited release durations of around 20 hours, while formulation F3, containing Tween 20 as a single surfactant, released the drug within 14 hours due to the higher hydrophilicity of Tween 20. These findings highlight that surfactant combinations enhanced both entrapment efficiency and sustained drug release, with maximum controlled release observed for up to 24 hours.

Based on the encapsulation efficiency and *in vitro* drug release profiles, formulations F6 and F8 were identified as the most effective, demonstrating superior entrapment efficiency and prolonged drug release.

This study successfully formulated and evaluated Gingerol Niosomes using non-ionic surfactants, demonstrating promising results in terms of encapsulation efficiency and sustained drug release. Among the formulations tested, F6 and F8 exhibited superior performance, making them optimal candidates for further research in drug delivery systems. This work underscores the potential of niosomes as versatile and efficient carriers for anti-

cancer drugs, paving the way for advancements in targeted drug delivery with minimized side effects.

Future studies can focus on clinical evaluations of these formulations to validate their efficacy and safety *in vivo*. The insights from this research contribute to the growing body of knowledge on nanocarrier systems, promising better therapeutic outcomes for various diseases.

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